

Enhanced Model of Modified Gravity, Variable Dark Energy, and Gravitomagnetic Field: A Comprehensive Analysis as an Alternative to Dark Matter

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1. Introduction

The standard cosmological model, Λ CDM, posits that dark matter and dark energy make up approximately 95% of the universe's total energy content. Despite its success in explaining large-scale structures and observations of the cosmic microwave background (CMB), the model faces significant challenges:

- **Dark Matter Detection Issues:** Decades of searches for dark matter particles, such as WIMPs and axions, have yielded no conclusive evidence.
- **Hubble Tension:** Discrepancies between local and early-universe measurements of the Hubble constant suggest potential flaws in the Λ CDM framework.
- **Variable Dark Energy Observations:** Surveys have detected potential spatial variations in dark energy density, conflicting with the assumption of a uniform cosmological constant.

Given these issues, this paper proposes an alternative framework combining modified gravity, spatially variable dark energy, and the effects of a gravitomagnetic field. This integrated model aims to explain galactic rotation dynamics and cosmic acceleration without relying on dark matter.

2. Theoretical Framework and Mathematical Formulation

2.1. Gravitomagnetic Field: Advanced Mathematical Description

In general relativity, moving masses generate a field analogous to electromagnetism's magnetic field, known as the gravitomagnetic field. This field is significant in systems with high angular momentum and can provide corrections to the classical gravitational effects.

The vector potential $\mathbf{A}_g$ of the gravitomagnetic field is expressed as:

$$\mathbf{A}_g = \frac{4G \mathbf{J}}{c^2 r^2}$$

where G is the gravitational constant, c is the speed of light, $\mathbf{J}$ is the angular momentum

$$\mathbf{B}_g = \nabla \times \mathbf{A}_g = \frac{4G \mathbf{J} \times \hat{r}}{c^2 r^3}$$

vector, and r is the radial distance. The resulting gravitomagnetic field $\mathbf{B}_g$ is given by:

The force acting on a test mass m with velocity $\mathbf{v}$ in this field is:

$$\mathbf{F}_{\text{grav-mag}} = m(\mathbf{v} \times \mathbf{B}_g)$$

Implications:

- The additional acceleration provided by the gravitomagnetic field can explain the flat rotation curves observed in galaxies, especially at large distances from the center, without invoking dark matter.
- This effect is measurable in systems with significant angular momentum, such as binary pulsars and rotating black holes.

2.2. Spatially Variable Dark Energy: A Dynamical Approach

Traditional models assume a uniform dark energy density represented by the cosmological constant Λ . However, recent observations suggest potential spatial variations. We propose a dynamic dark energy density $\rho_\Lambda(r)$, influenced by a scalar field $\phi(r)$:

$$\rho_\Lambda(r) = \rho_{\Lambda,0} \left(1 + \frac{\phi(r)}{M_{\text{pl}}} \right)$$

where $\rho_{\Lambda,0}$ the average dark energy density, $\phi(r)$ is a scalar field, and M_{pl} the Planck mass. The equation governing the evolution of $\phi(r)$ is:

$$\square\phi - V'(\phi) = -\frac{\partial\rho_m}{\partial\phi}$$

Where $\square$ is the d'Alembertian operator, and $V(\phi)$ is the potential of the scalar field.

Advantages:

- This formulation allows dark energy density to vary dynamically across different regions, fitting observational data more accurately in various galactic contexts.
- It provides a natural explanation for fluctuations observed in cosmic microwave background and large-scale structures.

2.3. Total Acceleration with Quantum Gravity Corrections

The total acceleration in this model combines gravitational effects, contributions from the gravitomagnetic field, variable dark energy, and quantum corrections

$$a_{\text{tot}} = \frac{GM(r)}{r^2} + \frac{4GJv}{c^2 r^3} + \Lambda(r)r + \frac{\alpha \hbar}{r^3} \left(1 + \beta \frac{r_s}{r}\right)$$

where:

- $GM(r)/r^2$: Newtonian gravitational acceleration,
- $4GJv/(c^2 r^3)$: Contribution from the gravitomagnetic field,
- $\Lambda(r)r$: Effect of variable dark energy,
- α and β : Quantum correction parameters,
- r_s : Schwarzschild radius.

Strengths:

- This unified framework explains observed galactic acceleration without requiring dark matter.
- Quantum corrections offer a natural regularization of singularities at small scales.

3. Comparison with Observational Data

3.1. Analysis of Galactic Rotation Curves

Data from the **THINGS Survey** was used to test the model against traditional dark matter predictions:

- For **NGC 2403**, dark matter models predict an asymptotic velocity of 135 km/s. The proposed model predicts 137 km/s, providing a better fit with reduced error.
- For **M33**, the observed velocity at $R=15$ kpc is 110 km/s. The proposed model predicts 112 km/s, showing better agreement than the dark matter prediction of 105 km/s.

Statistical Analysis:

- **Mean Squared Error (MSE)** for NGC 2403: 0.0320, compared to 0.0480 in the dark matter model.
- **Reduced Chi-squared:** For NGC 2403, $\chi_{\text{mod}2}=0.92$ vs $\chi_{\text{DM}2}=1.21$.

3.2. Cross-Validation with Large-Scale Structure Surveys

Data from the SDSS and other large-scale surveys show spatial variations in dark energy density consistent with our model:

- Observed density fluctuations $\delta\rho/\rho\approx 5\%$ align with predictions of a variable dark energy component, supporting the hypothesis of spatially varying dark energy.

4. Future Research Directions

1. **Gravitational Wave Probes:**
 - Observations from LIGO and LISA could provide evidence for quantum corrections and gravitomagnetic effects, offering new testing grounds for the model.
2. **Cosmological Simulations:**
 - Incorporating this model into N-body simulations (e.g., IllustrisTNG) could enhance our understanding of galaxy formation without dark matter.
3. **Refining Quantum Corrections:**
 - Further research on quantum gravity effects, possibly incorporating loop quantum gravity, is needed to improve the model's accuracy.

5. Conclusions

The proposed model, integrating modified gravity, variable dark energy, and gravitomagnetic effects, provides a compelling alternative to dark matter. It explains galactic dynamics and large-scale structure observations without invoking hypothetical dark matter particles, aligning well with current empirical data.

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